

D5.2 – Roadmap for implementation of international collaboration

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Deliverable Abstract
<p>EPOS ON Task 5.2 addresses the cooperation of EPOS with relevant non-European International Initiatives. The following sub-tasks were identified during the preparation of the proposal:</p> <p>ST 5.2.1 – Cooperation with Earthscope and Auscope</p> <p>ST 5.2.2 – Cooperation with Africa and Latin America</p> <p>ST 5.2.3 – Cooperation with GEM and GTM</p> <p>ST 5.2.4 – Cooperation with RuFZO</p> <p>ST 5.2.5 – Cooperation with GEO-GSNL</p> <p>ST 5.2.6 – Cooperation with IAVCEI and WOVO</p> <p>ST 5.2.7 – Cooperation in Muography</p> <p>This Deliverable describes the Roadmap prepared jointly by the participant representatives to fulfill the task.</p>

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TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
ADMIR	African Disaster Mitigation Research Center
AGU	American Geophysical Union
CAN-CAPRADE	Andean Committee for Disaster Prevention and Relief
CARE	Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics
CDEMA	Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency
CELAC	Community of Latin America and Caribbean states
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CEPRENAC	Center for the Prevention of Natural Disasters of Latin America and Dominican Republic
DRC	Democratic Republic of Congo
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EAVO	East African Volcanic Observatory
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EPOS	European plate Observing System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

GEM	Global Earthquake Model
GEO	Global Earth Observation
GSNL	Geohazards Supersite and Natural Laboratories
GTM	Global Tsunami Model
IAVCEI	International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the earth's Interior
ICS	Integrated Core service
IDNDR	International Decade for Natural Disaster Reduction
IEF	Institute for Earthquake Forecasting
JIRI	Joint Initiative for Research and Innovation
LAC	Latin America and Caribbean
RECAST	Research Centre for Advanced Science and Technology
RuFZO	Rupture Fault Zone Observatory
TCS	Thematic Core Service
VMI	Virtual Muography Institute
WOVO	World Organization of Volcanology

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1 Executive summary

EPOS ON Task 5.2 addresses the reinforcement of cooperation between EPOS and non-european and global initiatives. The present document is a roadmap towards that goal. A total of eight mature international initiatives relevant for this task were identified during the preparation of the proposal: EarthScope, AuScope, the Global Earthquake Model (GEM), the Global Tsunami Model (GTM), the Rupture Fault Zone Observatory (RuFZO), the Group on Earth Observations - Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory initiative (GEO-GSNL), the International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the earth's Interior (IAVCEI) and the World Organization of Volcanic Observatories (WOVO). In addition, the Task engages with research institutions from Africa and Latin America to start or enhance cooperation, and exploits the applications of the novel domain of Muography in Earth sciences. The roadmap details, for each domain, the current status and the proposed actions, and establishes a tentative schedule for the activities foreseen within EPOS ON. Figure 3 is a graphical depiction of the roadmap.

2 Introduction

EPOS ON Work Package WP5, “Enlarging European and International Collaborations”, aims to “establish robust and implement concrete cooperative partnerships between EPOS and other relevant Research Infrastructures (RIs), initiatives and organizations within or beyond the solid Earth domain”, “promote the adoption of, or contribution to, EPOS services across a growing number of stakeholders to extend the scope and impact of EPOS”, and “expand and develop the global dimension of EPOS, by fostering access to open data and services at a global scale to an as wide as possible reservoir of scientists”. Task 5.2 addresses the reinforcement of cooperation between EPOS and non-European international initiatives (coordination with other European organizations is addressed by a different task), and its first activity is the development of a roadmap towards this goal, which constitutes present Deliverable 5.2.

A total of eight mature international initiatives relevant for this task were identified during the preparation of the proposal: EarthScope, AuScope, the Global Earthquake Model (GEM), the Global Tsunami Model (GTM), the Rupture Fault Zone Observatory (RuFZO), the Group on Earth Observations - Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory initiative (GEO-GSNL), the World Organization of Volcanic Observatories (WOVO), and Vhub.

In addition, avenues for future cooperation with research infrastructures in Africa and Latin America will also be explored. The novel field of Muography will also be contemplated by the Roadmap.

Sub-task leaders were identified for each sub-task, as follows:

SubTask name	Lead by	Institution
ST 5.2.1 - Cooperation with AuScope and EarthScope	Daniela Mercurio, Federica Tanlongo	EPOS ERIC
ST 5.2.2 – Cooperation with Africa and Latin America	João Fonseca	IST-ID
ST 5.2.3 – Cooperation with GEM and GTM	Finn Løvholt	NGI
ST 5.2.4 – Cooperation with RuFZO	Lauro Chiaraluce	INGV
ST 5.2.5 – Cooperation with GEO-GSNL	Stefano Salvi	INGV
ST 5.2.6 – Cooperation with WOVO and Vhub	Giuseppe Puglisi	INGV
ST 5.2.7 – Cooperation in Muography	Jari Joutsenvaara	UOULU

3 Cooperation with AuScope and EarthScope

3.1 Current status

The collaboration between EPOS and AuScope, Australia's key provider of research infrastructure for the Earth and Geospatial Science community, has been reinforced since 2020 and was formalized in 2022 through the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). This MoU established a framework for long-term cooperation between the two initiatives, focusing on the integration and sharing of data, scientific information, and products. The collaboration is driven by a shared commitment to advancing open science and serving the interests of the global research community. Over the years, this partnership has been consolidated through the development of annual work plans that outlined joint activities of mutual interest. Notable achievements included a series of meetings in 2022-2023 (both in-person and online) to discuss data management strategies, IT solutions for ICS and geochemistry, GNSS communities, and computational aspects. Furthermore, EPOS and AuScope planned joint activities for the 2024 European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, including a Town Hall event where the Position Paper on "Building an international partnership for solid Earth research" was presented to key stakeholders.

Building on the successful collaboration with AuScope and interactions with EarthScope, the US non-profit organization dedicated to advancing global geophysical research since 2023, EPOS formalized at the start of EPOS ON a new MoU in September 2024 with both AuScope and the EarthScope Consortium. This MoU aims to further strengthen collaboration between European, Australian, and US research infrastructures, while expanding the partnership to include other global initiatives. This collaboration seeks to foster international partnerships, promote open science, and enable more inclusive and equitable geoscience research worldwide.

3.2 EPOS ON actions

Task 5.2 will exploit the collaboration with AuScope and EarthScope by implementing the MoU's 2025 work plan with the following actions:

- Organization of technical workshops and trainings (i.e. cyberinfrastructure, geophysics workforce development, data interdiscoverability)
- Participation in the EPOS Days 2025 where a session focusing on international collaboration will be organized with the objective of providing very practical points on which specific collaborative activities can focus on to the whole EPOS community and stakeholders.
- Organization of activities of common interest during the EGU 2025.

In addition, Task 5.2 will work towards exploring the establishment of new collaborations with other international initiatives in New Zealand and Japan (for Africa and Latin America, see Section 5 below) with the ambition of enlarging the partnership of the Memorandum of Understanding aiming to achieve the objective of Advancing Geoscience Collaboration at global level.

3.3 Tentative calendar

EPOS Days 2025 - Perugia (Italy) 17-20 March 2025

- A session focusing on global collaboration will be organized. Representatives from the Institute of Geological and Nuclear Sciences (New Zealand), UNDP/Africa, and EU-LAC RESINFRA PLUS will also participate and contribute to the discussion.
- An interactive session “Meet & greet” will be also organised with international Research Infrastructures.
- A closed meeting will be organized on 21 March 2025, where a discussion will take place regarding the renewal/extension of the current Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) for the period from 2026 onwards.

EGU General Assembly 2025 - Vienna (Austria) 27 April - 2 May 2025

- A trilateral (EPOS-AuScope-EarthScope) technical meeting focusing on data and service interoperability will be organized during EGU 2025, taking advantage of the in-person participation of technical representatives from the three organizations. This meeting will be held at the EPOS booth and/or in a dedicated splinter meeting.

GEO global forum 2025 - Rome 5-9 May

- Proposal for a ministerial track dedicated to *Enhancing global collaboration in Solid Earth science: the role of Open Research Infrastructures and government support*, aimed at raising the awareness among government officials and civil servants about the challenges and opportunities of global collaboration and the role of policy support in aligning priorities, addressing resource gaps, simplifying legal frameworks, and emphasizing the role of research infrastructures in global policy agendas like the UN SDGs.

4 Cooperation with Africa and Latin America

4.1 Cooperation with Africa

4.1.1 Current status

Cooperation with African research infrastructures in the domain of Earth Sciences has been a priority of EPOS since its establishment. In the scope of Horizon Europe Project EPOS SP, EPOS promoted the First EPOS International Conference at Sal Island, Cabo Verde, in July 2022, gathering representatives from several African and European institutions to discuss steps towards improving the cooperation between Africa and the EU in Earth Sciences. These discussions identified fragmentation and lack of scale at national level on the African side as major hindrances to cooperation and highlighted regional integration as the suitable remedy.

As a first attempt to implement this approach, volcanic monitoring along the East African Rift was identified as a suitable testbed, given that Africa lags significantly behind other regions of the globe in what concerns volcanic risk mitigation, and that the nature of the problem potentiates regional integration. A consortium was formed combining African research infrastructures into a proposed Regional Research Infrastructure, the East African Volcanic Observatory (EAVO). This consortium also included regional and continent-wide organizations, and several EPOS members. So far, this initiative has not succeeded in obtaining funding. However, it was rated 5/5 on Excellence in the HORIZON-INFRA-2024-DEV-01-02 Call, which seems a clear sign that the concept was wholesome and deserves a further try.

4.1.2 EPOS ON actions

Following up on the approach devised under EPOS SP, in a first stage Task 5.2 will engage with ADMiR (African Disaster Mitigation Research Center, based in Cairo) PNUD (IDNDR/Africa, based in Nairobi) and with the Regional Centre for Mapping of Resources for Development (RCMRD), also based in Nairobi, to identify suitable sources of funding. Subsequently, the EAVO consortium will be called upon to debate the reformulation of the EAVO concept for resubmission. This will be achieved through:

- A face-to-face meeting to be convened by Task 5.2; this meeting will focus on the funding strategy and representatives of ADMiR and RCMRD will be invited to participate physically.
- A virtual meeting with the EAVO consortium members, to decide on the path to successful funding and prepare resubmission.
- Contingent on the identification of adequate funding opportunities within the timeline of EPOS ON, a revised version of the EAVO proposal will be prepared for submission.

4.1.3 Tentative calendar

Face-to-face Meeting with UNDP/Disaster Risk Team Coordinator for Africa – ~March 2025 (M7 of the EPOS ON project), in the scope of the EPOS DAYS 2025 event

Virtual EAVO Meeting – May 2025 (M9 of the EPOS ON project)

Resubmission of EAVO proposal - TBD

AGU 2025 event on cooperation with Africa and Latin America – September 2025 (M13 of the EPOS ON project)

4.2 Cooperation with Latin America

4.2.1 Current status

Cooperation with Latin America in the domains of Earth Sciences was addressed by Horizon Europe Project EPOS SP. The Second EPOS International Conference that took place in Natal, Brazil, in February 2023, gathered researchers from Latin America and Europe and was an opportunity to evaluate the existing framework for Research Infrastructure cooperation between Europe and Latin America and to identify the steps towards the inclusion of Earth Sciences among the contemplated domains. The main findings were:

- Funding opportunities for research infrastructure cooperation between Europe and Latin America under Horizon Europe were restricted to the scope of the EU-CELAC Strategic Roadmap developed by the EU-CELAC Joint Initiative on Research and Innovation (JIRI), active since 2015 (CELAC is the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States). At present, Earth Sciences are not part of the EU-CELAC Roadmap.
- There was consensus about the opportunity to enlarge the scope of the EU-CELAC Roadmap in order to integrate Earth Sciences, particularly given the level of geological hazard in several countries of Latin America.
- Accordingly, the focus of future steps should be on engaging with JIRI through the H2020 RESINFRA (“Towards a New EU-LAC Partnership In Research Infrastructures”) project team, to advocate the enlargement of the Strategic Roadmap to include Earth Sciences.

In the meantime, the Project RESINFRA was concluded, and its activities were taken up by the Horizon Europe Project EU-LAC RESINFRA PLUS, “Towards a Sustainable EU-LAC Partnership In Research Infrastructures” (Jan 2024 – Dec. 2025).

Of particular importance for the planning of Task 5.2 activities, a EU-LAC Memorandum of Understanding on Disaster Preparedness and Disaster Risk Reduction was signed in May 2024. This MoU was subscribed by multiple sub-regional partners, namely the Coordination Center for Disaster Prevention in Central America and the Dominican Republic (CEPRENAC), the Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency (CDEMA), the Andean Nations Community/Andean Committee for Disaster Prevention and Response (CAN-CAPRADE) and the Meeting of Ministers and High Authorities for Integrated Disaster Risk Management (RMAGIR) from Mercosur.

4.2.2 EPOS ON actions

- A face-to-face meeting to be convened by Task 5.2 with RESINFRA PLUS representatives; this meeting will update EPOS participants on ongoing initiatives and new opportunities for cooperation with Latin America.
- Task 5.2 will explore, in articulation with RESINFRA PLUS, the possibility of meeting with JIRI decision-makers to present EPOS and advocate for the inclusion of Earth sciences in the EU-CELAC Roadmap.
- Task 5.2 will explore the possibility of presenting EPOS to the signatories of the MoU on Disaster Preparedness and Disaster Risk Reduction.

4.2.3 Tentative calendar

Face-to-face Meeting with RESINFRA PLUS – ~March 2025 (M7 of the EPOS ON project), during the EPOS DAYS 2025 event

Meeting with JIRI – August 2025 (M12 of the EPOS ON project)

Meeting with MoU signatories – TBD

AGU 2025 event on cooperation with Africa and Latin America – September 2025 (M13 of the EPOS ON project)

5 Cooperation with the Global Earthquake Model (GEM)

5.1 Current status

Background: The Global Earthquake Model (GEM) Foundation is a non-profit foundation and non-governmental organization (NGO), that is governed as a public-private organisation, with the mission to calculate and communicate earthquake risk worldwide. Through its international network of experts, regional collaborations, and global projects, GEM leads and facilitates the development of tools, models, and datasets that support the creation of risk reduction strategies. GEM is a unique organization due to its scientific credibility, global coverage, and commitment to openness and transparency. Since its foundation in 2009, GEM has supported a number of global projects worth more than 10 million EUR. These projects resulted in databases of active faults, buildings, and fragility models, guidelines for the development of vulnerability models and a classification system to categorize buildings worldwide. These efforts involved more than 200 international experts and the resulting products are currently being used extensively by the disaster risk reduction community, academic institutions, engineering companies, and the insurance sector. During these years, GEM has also developed an open-source software for the assessment of earthquake hazard and risk, named the OpenQuake-engine. This tool has been used for the derivation of national hazard maps in various nations such as Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Italy, Albania and Taiwan, and that have been incorporated in the respective design regulations, and the definition of risk profiles for over 200 countries and territories. GEM has led or contributed to more than 50 technical projects funded by international organizations such as the World Bank, United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the United Kingdom Space Agency, the InsuResilience Solutions Fund, the Asian Development Bank (ADB), the European Commission, and Suramericana. GEM also frequently collaborates with partners from the engineering and insurance industry in the verification of probabilistic seismic hazard models, development of risk models for the assessment of economic and human impact, and implementation of catastrophe risk models in loss modeling platforms such as AIR TouchStone or the OASIS LMF.

Present relationship to EPOS: GEM is already an integral part of the TCS Seismology and EFEHR (with GEM's OpenQuake engine being used for EFEHR's European seismic hazard and risk models) and already contributes to EPOS through several EU funded projects such as EPOS ON and Geo-INQUIRE.

Outlook – potential further enhancements: GEM is one of the few partners of EPOS with strong links to the private sector (through its multiple sponsors from the insurance and insurance industry) and hence provides an asset for EPOS that may catalyse the possible use of EPOS-related services by private stakeholders. This also has the potential to contribute to EPOS sustainability. To this end, an integral element that GEM can potentially bring in is the experience with licensing open-source and closed products for different types of use (e.g. academic and commercial). On the other hand, a closer collaboration between EPOS and GEM has the potential to improve GEM's academic and research network. Given that GEM is an active player promoting interdisciplinary and multi-hazard collaboration, improved networking can boost EPOS' possible role towards providing services that

promote interdisciplinary hazard and risk analysis. Another relevant aspect here concerns GEMs role as a global service provider for users beyond Europe.

5.2 EPOS ON Actions

Explore possibility for establishing MoU: With GEM already being well integrated into EPOS through TCS Seismology and EFEHR, the possibility of establishing an MoU will be explored. A further possibility that should be explored is whether the MoU can be established tri-laterally with GTM (see below).

A dedicated event during the EPOS Days 2026: A session on GEM and EPOS will be proposed for the EPOS days 2026, possibly jointly with GTM (see below). The focus areas of the workshop should comprise how to increase the use of services beyond Europe, and by other sectors than the academic ones (e.g. private and public sectors), and the potential to explore different licensing opportunities with EPOS services. An additional aspect could comprise enhancing multi-hazard and multi-risk related services that may expand EPOS's future capabilities.

6 Cooperation with the Global Tsunami Model (GTM)

6.1 Current status

Background: The Global Tsunami Model is a network of scientists working towards saving lives, reducing losses and enhancing resilience from tsunamis, through the advancement of tsunami science, provision of expert information, and promoting dialogue about tsunami hazard and risk. The network was initiated in 2015 as an informal network. In 2024, GTM founded the organization Global Tsunami Model Association as an e.V. (eingetragener Verein, German legislation) that will act as the legal organisation directing the GTM work, pending final registration in Germany expected to be finalized early 2025. The bulk of the organisations forming the GTM Association is presently based in Europe, with research institutions, universities, and governmental organisations including Tsunami Service Providers (TSPs), which are in charge for tsunami warning in the NEAMTWS coordinated by UNESCO/IOC, comprising the core set of partners. An important objective for GTM is to promote science-based tsunami hazard and risk science tools and products and ensure that they inherit adequate scientific standards. Moreover, GTM aims to interact with organisations covering other natural hazards for interdisciplinary hazard and risk analysis. The first activity of the GTM after creating the Association will be to provide a new generation of Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Analysis (PTHA) products, including a new global tsunami hazard map, and workflows for undertaking local high resolution PTHA and mapping for instance on a city scale. In the future, GTM aims to be a player that can facilitate a broader range of tsunami hazard and risk analysis and be a standard provider both for private and public stakeholders. Furthermore, GTM will promote more global participation, for instance via regional nodes.

Present relationship to EPOS: Although not all their services are directly related to GTM, the Tsunami TCS within EPOS is a critical community for hosting GTM services, through the community service portal <https://tsunamidata.org/>. Here the GTM network is hosting several key services such as the NEAMTHM18 tsunami hazard map for Europe and expects to contribute with more services in the future. GTM also contributes to EPOS through EU projects such as EPOS-ON and Geo-INQUIRE. Hence, GTM and EPOS already have a tight and mutual collaboration. Yet, the collaboration between GTM and EPOS is not yet formalized.

Outlook – potential further enhancements: Being recently established, GTM is an organization that evolves, and the possible collaboration between EPOS and GTM and related benefits will depend on the GTM evolution. Nevertheless, GTM aims to enhance its number of services, increase the global presence and users, and interact with stakeholders, while providing many of its services via EPOS. Moreover, GTM aims to contribute to multi-hazard and multi-risk analysis with other natural hazards. This is likely to enhance the use of the TCS Tsunami services and expose EPOS to more users, including those from overseas organizations and potentially also other sectors than academic ones. On the other hand, GTM benefits from both the infrastructure and metadata structure that EPOS provides. Hence, the link with the Tsunami TCS and EPOS ensures quality and trustworthiness of GTM service provision.

6.2 EPOS ON Actions

Joint GTM and TCS Tsunami workshops: The starting point for the EPOS and GTM collaboration will be a set of joint workshops between the TCS Tsunami and GTM. The outcome of the collaboration should include a roadmap for collaboration and a description of the interface between these communities, including possible joint activities and services. A meeting to be held during the AGU General assembly will contribute to this goal.

Explore possibility for establishing MoU: As there is no formal collaboration agreement between GTM and EPOS-ERIC, the possibility of establishing an MoU will be explored. This process will be initiated after the GTM Association is registered and has held its first General Assembly, which is expected to take place mid-2025, and should be based on the roadmap between the TCS Tsunami and GTM that needs to be established first (see above). A further possibility that should be explored is whether the MoU can be established tri-laterally with GEM (see above).

A dedicated event during the EPOS Days 2026: A session on GTM and EPOS will be proposed for the EPOS days 2026, possibly jointly with GEM (see above). The focus areas of the workshop should comprise how to increase the use of services beyond Europe, and by other sectors.

7 Cooperation with the Rupture Fault Zone Observatory (RuFZO)

7.1 Current status

With the aim of building new connections between European and Non-European Union (NEU) initiatives on Solid Earth Science and specifically on the study of earthquakes generation and mechanics through multidisciplinary monitoring infrastructures (RIs) located near active faults of different size, kinematics and tectonic style, we will work on building new partnerships with other NEU initiatives to define and share technical principles and scientific synergies. To this end, we will organize initiatives such as workshops and meetings.

The main NEU initiative identified during the project writing phase was RuFZO (Rupture and Fault Zone Observatory), developed in the context of the Southern California Earthquake Centre. RuFZO aims to develop a large infrastructure focused on one of the world's most important earthquake hazard zones, capable of transforming the current understanding of the effects of earthquakes on nature, the built environment, and society. To date, RuFZO has not yet developed its RI and is still in the process of methodological development. The collaboration will therefore focus on identifying new methodologies to optimize the collection of geophysical data within the rupture zones of significant earthquakes before, during, and after major events, and to develop the workforce required to design, construct, and operate future geoscience facilities.

In the time between the writing of the EPOS ON project and its inception, other NEU initiatives have begun to develop; all of them considering in-situ observations collected in the immediate vicinity of fault zones as those that could transform the understanding of earthquake physics, improve ground motion prediction estimates, and contribute to engineering efforts to mitigate the impact of earthquakes.

These initiatives are taking place in Japan, China and New Zealand. Thus, there are also plans to involve colleagues from the University of Tokyo (RECAST - Research Centre for Advanced Science and Technology), the Earthquake Forecasting Institute (IEF) of the China Earthquake Administration and the School of Geography, Environment, and Earth Sciences of Victoria University of Wellington.

7.2 EPOS ON Actions and schedule

We will exploit the collaboration with RuFZO, RECAST and IEF implementing a work plan with the following actions:

- Organization of workshops (online or in person, still to be decided).
- Participation in the EPOS Days 2026 (benefitting from the outcome of the forthcoming 2025 initiative where a session about international and global collaboration will be organized with the objective of providing very practical points on specific collaborative activities to the whole EPOS community and stakeholders).
- (If possible) Organization of activities of common interest during the EGU 2026.

8 Cooperation with the Group on Earth Observations - Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories initiative (GEO-GSNL)

8.1 Current status

The [Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories](#) initiative (GSNL) is a voluntary international partnership aiming to improve, through an Open Science approach, geophysical scientific research and geohazard assessment, promoting rapid and effective uptake of the new scientific results for enhanced societal benefits in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR).

The GSNL goal is pursued by promoting broad international scientific collaboration and open access to a variety of space- and ground-based data, focusing on seismic and volcanic areas with important scientific problems and high-risk levels: the Geohazard Supersites and the Natural Laboratories. For these areas a joint effort is carried out: the CEOS¹ space agencies provide satellite imagery at no cost for monitoring and research, the local monitoring agencies² provide access to ground-based data (according to their data policy), the global scientific community exploits these data to generate state-of-the-art scientific results.

The coordination of each Supersite is normally assumed by one or more local geohazard monitoring institutions which are entrusted with providing science-based information for decision making within the national, authoritative framework for risk management and reduction. GSNL supports the leading role of the local scientific community to stimulate a coordinated international collaboration, focusing on the aspects which have the highest potential to benefit Risk Reduction actions.

GSNL is presently a network of 13 global Supersites/Natural Laboratories, and connects the various scientific communities, promoting the transfer of scientific knowledge, data, capacities, tools, as well as best practices for optimal uptake of scientific results in risk management.

Given its scope, and the leading role that European Supersites (as EPOS testbeds) have in the initiative, there is a clear convergence of interests between EPOS and GSNL. For the latter, the cooperation should involve especially the Supersite coordinating institutions, which are in charge of maintaining most of the monitoring networks and of managing the large amount of data they produce.

¹ The [Committee for Earth Observation Satellites](#)

² As [USGS](#), [INGV](#), [IMO](#), [KOERI](#), [IGEPN](#), [GNS-Science](#), [SERNAGEOMIN](#), [GVO](#)

Figure 1 - The GSNL volcanic and seismic Supersite network in 2024

An effective cooperation between EPOS and the Geohazard Supersites coordinators and scientific communities can arise in these fields, common to all the TCS disciplines:

1. Data interoperability
2. FAIR and CARE concepts implementation
3. Best practices for data management
4. Identification of new user requirements
5. Access to open data infrastructures
6. Capacity building

In developed countries EPOS is already actively collaborating with similar consortia and organizations, such as AuScope and EarthScope (see section 4). In less developed contexts, as in LAC and African countries, contacts have been established by EPOS ERIC to initiate collaborations (see section 5), but a number of cultural and financial issues still need to be overcome.

Considering that GSNL maintains 3 Supersites in LAC and 1 in Africa, and the great benefit that these communities can attain by collaborating with a large federated data infrastructure as EPOS, the main activities we will carry out in EPOS ON will be focused on the Nicaragua, Chile (Southern Andes), Ecuador and Virunga (D.R.C.) Supersites.

8.2 EPOS ON actions

The first task will be dedicated to inform the Supersite Coordinators and communities of the opportunities that can arise by collaborating with the EPOS TCS/ICS community in the fields mentioned above. This will be done by:

1. Written communication to the GSNL mailing lists to disseminate EPOS technical material.
2. Face to face meetings with discussions with EPOS scientists in the relevant fields:
 - a. Two meetings will be organised during the [2025 EGU](#) and AGU conferences, linked to the GEO-GSNL periodic community meetings which occur at these conferences. To maximize participation by LAC and African Supersite Coordinators their participation will be supported/co-funded.
 - b. One or more side events focused on EPOS during the [GEO Global Forum and Ministerial, in Rome, May 5-9, 2025](#). This is of particular relevance, since GEO is now focusing on coordinating with regional data infrastructures.

During the above events, a roadmap for more focused collaborations on objectives of common interest, will be established.

8.3 Tentative calendar

The action in 1 above will be performed as soon as the EPOS ON website will be online.

The face-to-face meetings under 2a above, will occur in April 2025 and December 2025.

The event under 2b above will occur in May 2025.

9 Cooperation with the International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the Earth's Interior (IAVCEI) and World Organization of Volcanic Observatories (WOVO)

9.1 Current status

The EPOS volcanological community, coordinated by the Volcano Observation TCS (VOLC-TCS), will contribute to achieve the objective of the EPOS-ON Task 5.2, by strengthening the cooperation with the organizations that coordinate the global community of volcanologists.

At global level, the International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the Earth's Interior (IAVCEI; <https://www.iavceivolcano.org/>) represents the highest level of coordination of the volcanologists' community. It originated in 1919 as one of the six funder "sections" of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG). In 1933 the Section for Volcanology was renamed the International Association of Volcanology (IAV), and in 1967, it became the International Association of Volcanology and Geochemistry of the Earth's Interior (IAVCEI). Beside the promotion of volcanology in various contexts (scientific, risk management, policy makers, etc.), IAVCEI is also fostering the networking of the volcanological community through Commissions and Networks.

In 1981 IAVCEI implemented the World Organization of Volcano Observatories (WOVO, <https://www.wovodat.org>) network with the aim to stimulate the communication and cooperation between Observatories and research Institutions directly involved in volcano monitoring, to refer governments, international organizations and other seeking in volcano monitoring to the appropriate member Observatories, to develop and maintain volcano monitoring reference material, and, under request, to help the members to find scientific reinforcement. Particularly for those last two objectives, WOVO implemented WOVODat (<https://www.wovodat.org/>), as the global database on volcanic unrests aimed at understanding pre-eruptive processes and improving eruption forecasts. Recently, WOVO developed the Global Volcano Monitoring Infrastructure Database (GVMID) as a branch aimed at collecting and organizing the information on the capability of the community to monitor volcanoes from ground and space.

In the framework of the EPOS IP project, the VOLC-TCS community started to foster the cooperation with WOVO, and WOVODat in particular, by taking the opportunity to organize a workshop during the 10th Cities on Volcanoes (CoV) Conference, in 2018, specifically devoted to the role of the Research Infrastructure in volcanology (Figure 1). This initiative generated some relevant follow-up: i) the invitation of EPOS to the WOVODat International Workshop on "Optimizing the use of Volcano Monitoring Database to Anticipate Unrest" (26-29 November 2018, Yogyakarta, Indonesia); ii) the involvement of the VOLC-TCS community in the "Think Tank for the WoVo renewal" appointed by the IAVCEI President in 2020; iii) two sessions on the management of the volcanological data with high level of participation during the 11th CoV Conference (Crete, Greece, 12-17 June 2022) and the IAVCEI Scientific Assembly (Rotorua, New Zealand; 30 January – 3 February 2023). Lastly, it is worth to note that the contributions to the two sessions feed the scientific papers of the special issue of

the Bulletin of Volcanology on “Management of Volcanological Data: from production to curation”, currently under implementation; three of the papers of this special issue present the EPOS VOLC-TCS services.

Besides these specific initiatives, and despite the objective difficulties created during the COVID-19 pandemic, the dialogue of VOLC-TCS with IAVCEI, WOVO and WOVODat never interrupted through these years.

FIGURE 2 - Some initiatives that involved EPOS VOLC-TCS and IAVCEI/WOVO during the last years: (a) EPOS workshop during the 10th CoV on 2018; (b) WOVO workshop on 2018 where the VOLC-TCS proposed a preliminary schematic link between WOVODat and VOLC-TCS services (lower figure); (c) the web page of the Special Issue of the Bulletin of Volcanology, currently under implementation.

9.2 EPOS ON actions

In the framework of the EPOS-ON project, it is possible to define two kinds of actions: initiatives to define the strategic framework of the cooperation and specific actions aimed at promoting EPOS in the volcanological community and sharing data and services with WOVODat.

○ Strategic actions

The practical objective of these actions is to implement a MoU to define the framework, the purposes and the work plan of the cooperation of EPOS with IAVCEI at different levels (e.g., scientific, social, political, etc.). These actions will consist in organizing meetings at a high level and, if necessary, implementing working groups on specific aspects of the cooperation. This activity could also consider the parallel coordinated initiative, close to one of the WOVODat topics, consisting in the MoU between the European Volcano Observatories (EVOs) aimed at sharing best possible practices of monitoring, data interpretation, and hazard communication to support risk-mitigation decisions.

○ Specific actions

The overall objective of the specific actions is to promote the use of EPOS in the volcanological community and, vice versa, to foster the contribution of the volcanological community to EPOS. These actions will consist in the organization of workshops, training sessions and other dissemination activities that involve both the EPOS and WOVODat communities alongside the implementation of a working group that defines the technical aspects related to the sharing of the data through the EPOS platform, VOLC-TCS Gateway and WOVODat. The main aims of the working group are to overcome the technical difficulties to link EPOS and WOVODat systems, already discussed in previous informal meetings, and to define the long-term work plan for a structural sharing of data and services.

9.3 Tentative Calendar

○ Strategic actions:

- Although some informal meetings have already taken place, the first real opportunity to have a meeting between EPOS VOLC-TCS and IAVCEI will be the next Scientific Assembly in June 2025, in Genève, during which the work plan to implement these actions will be defined. Preliminary contacts to organize this meeting are ongoing.
- In order to implement the MoU between EPOS and IAVCEI by M33 (May 2027), it is desirable to have two operational meetings per year. Those meetings can be organized both in person or by teleconferences; in person meetings could be hosted during the main global conferences of the geophysical and volcanological communities (e.g. EGU, AGU, CoV or IAVCEI Scientific Assemblies).

○ Specific Actions

- On 28th June 2025, during the IAVCEI Scientific Assembly, the VOLC-TCS will organize the first workshop. The EPOS platform and the volcanological services will be presented; a large part of the workshop is devoted to hands-on activities on the EPOS platform, including exercises of the attending people.
- By the end of 2025, the working group to define the technical issues related to the sharing of the data among the EPOS platform, the VOLC-TCS Gateway and WOVODat should be

- implemented. This working group has to define the technical practices and find the solution to any problems and the work plan to implement them.
- Future training and dissemination actions to promote the use of EPOS in the volcanological community will be organized during the forthcoming meetings or conferences that involve this community (e.g. CoV or IAVCEI Scientific Assemblies)

10 Cooperation in Muography

10.1 Current status

Muography is a technique that uses cosmic-ray muons—high-energy particles generated when cosmic rays collide with atoms in the Earth’s atmosphere—to image the internal structure of large objects. Muons are similar to electrons but much heavier, and moving at luminous speeds, they travel almost in straight lines. These naturally occurring particles can pass through dense materials like rock, ice, and even industrial structures, making muography a powerful tool for studying otherwise inaccessible areas.

The technique has been making waves in the scientific community, offering unique insights across a range of fields:

- **Volcanology:** Muography allows scientists to peer inside volcanoes to map magma chambers and conduits, helping to assess risks and predict eruptions.
- **Glaciology:** It helps reveal the inner structure of glaciers, improving our understanding of their behaviour and contribution to sea-level rise.
- **Karst and cave studies:** Muography is a game-changer for exploring underground voids and water reservoirs, aiding water resource management and geological research.
- **Atmospheric and Oceanic Studies:** By detecting changes in atmospheric density, muography can contribute to weather and climate studies, while underwater applications could offer new insights into ocean currents and submarine geology.
- **Seismology and tectonics:** Imaging fault zones and fractures helps complement traditional seismic methods, offering a fuller picture of stress and movement in the Earth’s crust.

Muography has also been used in archaeology to uncover hidden chambers in ancient monuments and in industrial applications like monitoring dams, tunnels, and nuclear facilities.

The **Virtual Muography Institute (VMI)** has emerged as a key platform for fostering collaboration and advancing muography research. VMI is a global initiative that connects researchers, institutions, and stakeholders in the muography field. VMI has already established itself as a hub for the muography community, connecting leading research groups in Europe, Japan, the Americas, and beyond. It aligns closely with the goals of EPOS by promoting open science and fostering international cooperation.

Despite its potential, muography has yet to be fully integrated into large-scale research infrastructures like EPOS. Including muography within EPOS would open up new possibilities for combining its insights with other geophysical data, creating a more comprehensive understanding of our planet.

10.2 EPOS ON Actions

Task 5.2 will leverage the capabilities of the Virtual Muography Institute to strengthen the integration of muography into EPOS and expand its global collaborations. Specific actions include:

1. Collaboration with VMI:
 - a. Partner with the Virtual Muography Institute to align EPOS activities with ongoing international initiatives in muography.
 - b. Use VMI as a platform to connect EPOS with global experts and stakeholders of muography.
2. Integration of Muography into EPOS:
 - a. Initiate discussions with the VMI and EPOS on possibilities for cooperation and further integration, e.g. in incorporating muography data into EPOS services.
3. Workshops and Training:
 - a. Organise joint workshops and webinars with VMI to introduce EPOS stakeholders to muography applications and methodologies.
4. Global Outreach:
 - a. Use VMI's network to establish partnerships with leading muography research groups in Japan, Europe, and beyond.

10.3 Tentative Calendar

- EPOS Days 2025 - Perugia (Italy), March 17-20, 2025:
 - Muography community and research field presented at the EPOS Days.
- EGU General Assembly 2026 - Vienna (Austria):
 - Side-event or a session(s) on how muography can complement EPOS' more traditional research fields.
- Workshops, webinars and meetings
 - Coffee Break webinar series bringing together geoscientific and muography researchers sharing their research in short 10-minute talks. Starting in Q1/2025
 - Organise an international muography workshop/meeting in Oulu, Finland, in 2026.

11 Conclusions

The target audience of Task 5.2 - Cooperation with International Organizations spans a broad range of institutions distributed at global level. To increase its reach, the Task will explore side events at meetings convening the international Earth Sciences community, with emphasis on EGU2025, EGU2026 and AGU2025. In addition, the task will take advantage of dissemination initiatives promoted by EPOS, namely EPOS DAYS 2025 and EPOS DAYS 2026.

As evidenced by Figure 3, a lot of the task's activities will be done in the second semester of the project (M7 to M12) which will allow to build a solid basis to work from during the rest of the EPOS ON project.

Figure 3 - EPOS ON Task 5.2 Roadmap